

Effect of Fenticonazole Therapy on Vaginal Candidiasis: A Comparison Versus Clotrimazole

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Abstract

Background: Vaginal candidiasis (VC) is a leading cause of abnormal vaginal discharge after bacterial vaginosis at gynecologic clinics. The most common causative organism is *Candida albicans*, which is one of the vaginal normal floras.

Objectives: aim of this study was to compare the treatment effect of fenticonazole versus clotrimazole on vaginal candidiasis patients.

Methods: A total of 100 patients clinically compatible with Vulvovaginal candidiasis, diagnosis were confirmed by laboratory examination for *Candida* species were enrolled. All patients were randomly divided into two groups, group A received intra-vaginal Fenticonazole (600 mg) and Group B received intra-vaginal Clotrimazole (500 mg). Both group are followed up for four weeks and compared the treatment effects in terms of clinical and mycological features.

Results: Majority of the subjects (37%) were 31-45 years age group. No significant difference between the fenticonazole and clotrimazole group in terms of age, BMI, residential and socio-economic status ($p > 0.05$). Common risk factors of fungal vulvo-vaginitis are factors of frequent micturition, vulvar cleaning, and associated sexually transmitted diseases. Complete cure rate and recurrence rate were almost similar in both the group. Therapeutic efficacy of both the agents was similar after first week of treatment, but efficacy was significantly higher in fenticonazole group after 2nd or 4th week of treatment ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Fenticonazole has a broad spectrum antifungal agent highly effective and well tolerable against treatment of Vulvo-vaginal candidiasis.

Keywords: Clotrimazole, fenticonazole, efficacy, fungal vulvo-vaginitis, recurrence, risk factors.

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Introduction

Vaginal candidiasis (VC) is a leading cause of abnormal vaginal discharge for women [1, 2]. The most common pathogen, causing 80-90% of cases, is *Candida albicans* [2]. Recently, the British Association for Sexual Health and HIV (BASHH) suggests disease duration-based classification into acute VC and recurrent VC. The recurrent VC is defined as having at least 4 recurrences within a previous year, with at least 2 recurrences confirmed by either microscopic diagnosis or culture whilst having any symptoms [3]. Fenticonazole is an imidazole derivative with a broad spectrum of antimycotic. Clotrimazole is an imidazole antimycotic agent that was discovered in the 1960s. It has a specific chemical structure consisting of four aromatic rings, out of which one represents an imidazole ring [4]. Since Clotrimazole has been used in vulvovaginal candidiasis (VVC) for decades, fungal resistance against drugs seems to

be increasing. It causes more difficulty in treatment, but also affects healthcare expenditure. The incidence of resistance in patients with candidiasis is still high [5, 6]. However, oral Fluconazole and Clotrimazole vaginal tablet have been used as the current standard treatments of VVC [7]. Recently, a new imidazole fungicide has been introduced for VVC indication, named Sertaconazole [8]. This is an azole group of antifungal with benzothiofene structure similar to tryptophan in fungal plasma membrane, which facilitates the incorporation of Sertaconazole into fungal cells. Inhibition of biosynthesis of ergosterol by inactivating 14- α -demethylase enzyme results in formation of pores, bringing about a massive leak of cytoplasm and adenosine triphosphate (ATP) with consequent cell death. Sertaconazole also exerts a direct toxic effect on the fungal membrane. With the properties of new structure of this

imidazole derivative [9], we may come to the solution for VVC treatment. Clotrimazole was first registered as Canesten in Germany more than 45 years ago (in 1973) [10]. Approximately 70–75% of childbearing aged women experience symptomatic vulvovaginal candidosis at least once during their life and 40–50% will suffer from repeated episodes during their lifetime. About 5–8% of adult women may experience recurrent vulvovaginal candidosis (i.e., ≥ 4 episodes per year) [11]. The treatment of vulvovaginal candidosis depends on whether the infection is uncomplicated or complicated. Complicated cases comprise recurrent, severe and non-albicans vulvovaginal candidosis as well as vulvovaginal yeast infections during pregnancy and in subjects with immunocompromised conditions [12].

Aims & Objectives

The aim of this study to compare the effect of Fenticonazole versus Clotrimazole on vaginal candidiasis patients.

Materials and Methods

This was a cross sectional comparative observational hospital based study conducted in the department of dermatology, in a tertiary care hospital, India. Patients diagnosed with vulvovaginal candidiasis during the study period were enrolled.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients who are clinically compatible with Vulvovaginal candidiasis infections
- Cases who confirmed by laboratory examination for Candida species
- Patients age range of 18-70 years
- Patients who provide consent for the study
- Patients who discontinue any antifungal agents at least two weeks before enrollment

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients <18 years of age
- Patients with history of hypersensitivity toazole drugs
- Participants who not provide consent for the study

All subjects were randomized into two groups:

Group A: Patients received a single-dose intravaginal treatment with a Fenticonazole (600 mg)

Group B: Patients received a single dose intravaginal treatment with a Clotrimazole (500 mg)

All patients were follow-up for four weeks from the day of treatment.

Clinical and mycological assessments were recorded after 1 week of the therapy

Complete history, Socio-demographic data (age, marital history, occupation, education, residential area, socio-economic status) and clinical presentation of all the study participants were recorded. All patients were diagnosed by laboratory examination of KOH, microscopic examination, fungal culture and other relevant investigation.

Therapeutic efficacy was assessed by microbiological and clinical criteria 7 days and 1 month (when possible) after the single dose treatment.

The specimens were collected from the patient's vagina by clinicians on site using sterile cotton swabs. Swabs were transferred in sterile normal saline tubes at room temperature. They were determined for yeast pathogens as per standard guidelines.

Statistical Analysis

All the data were analyzed by using SSPS version 22. P value <0.05 considered as statistically significant

Results

A total of 100 diagnosed patients of vaginal candidosis were enrolled and analysed in the present study. All are randomly divided into two groups, fenticonazole group and clotrimazole group (50 each). Majority of the subjects (37%) were 31-45 years age group.

Most of them were (64%) residing at rural area, 88% were married, 47% belong to lower socio-economic status, 45% had house wife and 54% of women having normal body mass index.

Table 1: socio-demographic characteristics of the study participants

Socio-demographic characteristics		Fenticonazole group (n=50)	Clotrimazole group (n=50)	P value
Age group (in years)	18-30	7 (14%)	8 (16%)	0.98
	31-45	19 (38%)	18 (36%)	
	45-60	16 (32%)	15 (30%)	
	>60	8 (16%)	9 (18%)	
Marital status	Married	45 (90%)	43 (86%)	0.54
	Unmarried	5 (10%)	7 (14%)	
Residential area	Rural	31 (62%)	33 (66%)	0.68
	Urban	19 (38%)	17 (34%)	

BMI (kg/m ²)	Underweight	13 (26%)	10 (20%)	0.74
	Normal weight	27 (54%)	28 (56%)	
	Obese	10 (20%)	12 (24%)	
Occupation	Labour	18 (36%)	19 (38%)	0.96
	House wife	22 (44%)	23 (46%)	
	Student	6 (12%)	5 (10%)	
	Professional	4 (8%)	3 (6%)	
Socio-economic status	Lower	23 (46%)	24 (48%)	0.91
	Middle	21 (42%)	19 (38%)	
	Upper	6 (12%)	7 (14%)	

As risk factors of fungal vulvo-vaginitis, factors of frequent micturition, vulvar cleaning, and associated sexually transmitted diseases were summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Risk factors of fungal vulvo-vaginitis

Risk factors		Fenticonazole group	Clotrimazole group
Frequent micturition (>5times/day)	Present	19 (38%)	17 (34%)
	Absent	31 (62%)	33 (66%)
Toilet shower	Sometimes	22 (44%)	24 (48%)
	Every times	28 (56%)	26 (52%)
Vulvar cleansing	Sometimes	34 (68%)	30 (60%)
	Every times	16 (32%)	20 (40%)
Associated sexually transmitted diseases	Present	9 (18%)	10 (20%)
	Absent	41 (82%)	40 (80%)

Complete cure rate after treatment of fenticonazole and clotrimazole was almost similar, 76% in fenticonazole and 74% in clotrimazole group. Recurrence rate was 8% in fenticonazole whereas 6% in clotrimazole group.

Table 3: Comparison of treatment results among Fenticonazole and Clotrimazole group

Treatment results	Fenticonazole group (n=50)	Clotrimazole group (n=50)	P value
Complete cure	38 (76%)	37 (74%)	0.92
Recurrence	4 (8%)	3 (6%)	
Treatment failure	8 (16%)	10 (20%)	
Side effect	4 (8%)	3 (6%)	0.70

Therapeutic efficacy of both the agents was similar after first week of treatment, but efficacy was significantly higher in fenticonazole group after 2nd or 4th week of treatment (p<0.05)

Table 4: Therapeutic efficacy of both the agents on follow up period

Therapeutic efficacy		Fenticonazole group	Clotrimazole group	P value
After 7 th day of treatment	Disappearance of the signs and symptoms	27 (54%)	25 (50%)	0.94
	Negative Mycological tests	9 (18%)	8 (16%)	
On second follow up	Disappearance of the signs and symptoms	37 (74%)	29 (58%)	0.93
	Negative Mycological tests	29 (58%)	22 (44%)	
After complete four week therapy	Disappearance of the signs and symptoms	47 (92%)	39 (78%)	0.96
	Negative Mycological tests	44 (88%)	37 (74%)	

Discussion

Fenticonazole appeared to be well tolerated and highly effective azole antifungal agents against dermatophytes and *Candida* species. Topical treatment with Fenticonazole as a 2% cream or 100 mg ovules gave high cure rates in patients with

vaginal candidiasis [13].

In numerous clinical studies in part double blind Fenticonazole gave a favorable clinical outcome and comparable to the results obtained with reference compounds like econazole, miconazole and clotrimazole, respectively [14].

The signs and symptoms of VC are unique, including itchiness, curd-like vaginal discharge, and lesions on external genitalia such as erythematous skin, swelling and abrasion. However, the diagnosis of VC should not be based on only symptoms, but should also be confirmed by laboratory investigation

There is no significant differences in terms of socio-demographic characteristics among both the groups, our results are similar to the Anuvat R, et al [15] and Veraldi & Milani, et al [16].

Majority of the vulvovaginal candidiasis patients were belong to rural area and lower socio-economic class in current study, constant finding reported by Sobel JD, et al [17], this may be due to poor nutrition, lack of education, overcrowding and poor hygiene.

In this study most of the vulvovaginal candidiasis participants do not take toilet shower regularly and not cleaned their genitalia properly, accordance to the C Chayachinda, et al [18].

Our results demonstrate that the treatment of vaginal candidiasis with Fenticonazole ovules or clotrimazole tablets after a single dose regimen is highly effective and well tolerated, Fenticonazole was somewhat more effective than clotrimazole, concordance finding also reported by A. G. Lawrence, et al [19] and Brewster E, et al [20]. Highly significant improvements in symptoms, associated with disappearance of detectable *Candida* among both the group

In the present study treatments resulted were almost similar in both the group in terms of cure rate, recurrence rate and treatment failure an agreement with the Studd JW, et al [21] and F. Gorlero, et al [22].

Conclusion

We have concluded that Vulvo-vaginal candidiasis was higher in 31-45 years age group, rural population and lower socio-economic class peoples. No significant difference in terms of cure rate and recurrence rate of fenticonazole and clotrimazole, but fenticonazole was higher therapeutic efficacy than clotrimazole.

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